

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Lactic Acid by Potassium Peroxodisulphate, Catalysed by Silver Ions

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Oxidation of lactic acid by peroxodisulphate is very slow below 50°, but it has a measurable velocity at these temperatures in presence of silver ions such that the rate is proportional to the concentration of the catalysat. From the effect of increasing ionic strength, contributed by added electrolyte to the reacting solution, it is concluded that the rate decreases slightly with the increasing ionic strength, but H⁺ and K⁺ ions also have depressing action on the rate of the reaction.

The product of the oxidation has been identified mainly as acetaldehyde, formed by the rupture of C—C bond of COOH from the parent molecule and by its substitution by OH group. That formation of pyruvic acid under similar condition is extremely slow and no acetaldehyde formation could be identified from pyruvic acid solution, containing peroxodisulphate and Ag⁺ ions, lend support to the above mechanism for the oxidation of lactic acid.

King and Steinbach¹ found the kinetics of organic compounds by peroxodisulphate to be erratic in presence of the slightest impurity. Srivastava and Ghosh² stressed the use of highest possible pure chemicals for the study of the kinetics of oxidation with peroxodisulphate. Oxidation of lactic acid by common oxidising agents has also been investigated by several workers³. Levitt and Malinowski³ found the oxidation of isopropyl alcohol to be very slow below 50°. In the present communication, the silver ion-catalysed oxidation of lactic acid, i.e., a compound containing one COOH in place of methyl group of the isopropyl alcohol, has been investigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the chemicals used were of B. D. H., A. R. or of extra pure quality and solutions of all the reactants were prepared in bidistilled water. Calculated quantities of the solutions of desired concentration with the requisite amount of bidistilled water were taken in a Jena glass bottle, coated on the outside with black Japan to eliminate the possibility of any photochemical reaction; it was placed in a thermostat maintained at the desired temperature within the range $\pm 0.1^\circ$. Peroxodisulphate and silver nitrate solutions were placed separately in the same thermostat. When the reactants had attained the required temperature, calculated volume of peroxodisulphate was added into the reaction vessel, immediately followed by a known volume of silver nitrate solution, and the time was

1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 4779.

2. *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1953, **202**, 198.

3. Ghosh *et al.*, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1959, **11**, 62, 320; Levitt and Malinowski, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 4517; Barlet and Cotman, *ibid.*, 1949, **71**, 1419; Yost, *ibid.*, 1926, **48**, 152; Cone, *ibid.*, 1945, **67**, 78.

noted. Measured volumes of the reaction mixture were withdrawn at different intervals and the remaining peroxodisulphate was iodometrically estimated, as described by Szabo *et al.*⁴.

The results were found to be reproducible (Table I). As the concentrations of peroxodisulphate and silver nitrate were sufficiently low, the main contribution to the ionic strength was due to K_2SO_4 present (0.375). In most of the experiments the variation was found large for the first few constants, after which satisfactory first-order constants were obtained.

TABLE I

Lactic acid = 0.1M. $K_2S_2O_8 = 0.02M$. $AgNO_3 = 0.0005M$. $K_2SO_4 = 0.125M$.
Temp. = 35°.

Time.	Hypo.	$K/2.303 \times 10^4$.	Time.	Hypo.	$K/2.303 \times 10^4$.
0 min.	4.86 ml	..	120 min.	2.80 ml	19.95 min ⁻¹
20	4.40	21.55 min ⁻¹	140	2.56	19.90
40	3.98	21.68	160	2.32	20.07
60	3.66	20.51	180	2.12	20.01
80	3.32	20.70	210	1.84	20.08
100	3.06	20.00			Av. 20.16

$$K = 46.42 \times 10^{-4} \text{ min}^{-1}.$$

Effect of Peroxodisulphate Concentration.—Different concentrations of the oxidant were used. The average values of the first-order constants are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Temp. = 35°.

Initial conc. of peroxodisulphate (M)	..	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04
$K \times 10^4$ (min ⁻¹)	..	49.07	46.42	46.96	47.39

Thus there is no significant effect of the initial concentration of peroxodisulphate and the order of the reaction with respect to peroxydisulphate is unity.

Effect of Lactic Acid Concentration.—To determine the total order of the reaction, the effect of different concentrations of lactic acid, much above that of peroxodisulphate, on the reaction rate was studied. The results are summarised in Table III.

TABLE III

Temp. = 35°.

Lactic acid conc. (M)	..	0.05	0.10	0.20
$K \times 10^4$ (min ⁻¹)	..	55.64	46.42	43.55

Table III shows that the rate constants tend to decrease with increasing concentrations of lactic acid; the order of this reaction with respect to lactic acid, when calculated by isolation method between the two concentrations (0.2M and 0.1M), has been found to be -0.09 . It may be concluded that the reaction is of zero order with respect to lactic acid and that it has a slight retarding effect on the velocity of the reaction.

Effect of Silver Nitrate Concentration.—The silver ions for different concentrations of silver nitrate affect the first-order rate constants; the data are shown Table IV.

TABLE IV

AgNO ₃ (M)	..	0.00050	0.00025	0.0010	0.00125
$K \times 10^4$ (min ⁻¹)	..	46.42	60.89	103.46	134.96
K for unit conc. of Ag ⁺ ions	..	9.28	9.75	10.34	10.89

Thus the rate of the reaction increases with the increasing concentration of silver nitrate and this relationship is approximately linear.

Effect of Hydrogen-ion Concentration.—The change in hydrogen-ion concentration in the reaction mixture was effected by mixing different amounts of NaOH solution to lactic acid. Thus a constant amount of lactate was used in the reaction mixture at different pH. The values of the rate constants ($K \times 10^4$ min⁻¹) at 35° are 154.85 (pH 5.32), 146.68 (pH 4.82), and 125.53 (pH 4.37).

During the variation of H⁺-ion concentration from pH 4.37 to 5.32, there is considerable effect of hydrogen ions on the rate of the reaction. Higher concentrations of hydrogen ion in the reaction mixture were also produced by adding different amounts of sulphuric acid. requisite amounts of potassium sulphate were added to avoid the variations in the ionic strength and SO₄²⁻ ion concentration produced by adding different concentrations of sulphuric acid for the reaction.

TABLE V
Temp. = 35°.

H ₂ SO ₄ conc. (M)	..	0.01	0.02	0.04	0.08
$K \times 10^4$ (min ⁻¹)	..	45.90	43.55	44.31	45.59

Values of the rate constants, cited above, show that the rates of the reaction decrease with progressive increase in H⁺-ion concentration, but for the high concentration of the acid, the rate remains unaffected. It appears therefore that the oxidation is faster for lactate anion than for undissociated lactic acid.

Effect of Neutral Salts.—The effect of different neutral salts was studied in the oxidation of lactic acid. The average values of the rate constants in presence of different electrolytes are recorded in Table VI.

TABLE VI
Temp. = 35°.

Conc. of added electrolyte.	*Ionic strength.	$K \times 10^4$ (min ⁻¹).	Conc. of added electrolyte.	*Ionic strength.	$K \times 10^4$ (min ⁻¹).
Nil	..	78.34	MgSO ₄ 0.0625M	0.2500	59.92
K ₂ SO ₄ 0.2500M	0.750	40.37	KNO ₃ 0.2500	0.2500	27.19
K ₂ SO ₄ 0.1250	0.375	46.42	KNO ₃ 0.1250	0.1250	40.14
K ₂ SO ₄ 0.0625	0.187	51.49	KNO ₃ 0.0625	0.0625	46.47
MgSO ₄ 0.1250	0.500	55.32			

*Contributed by added electrolyte.

The rate constants decrease with increasing ionic strength and in presence of 0.125*M* of MgSO_4 , K_2SO_4 , and KNO_3 are 55.32×10^{-4} , 46.42×10^{-4} , and 40.14×10^{-4} , the ionic strength contributed by these salts being 0.50, 0.375, and 0.125 respectively. Hence it is clear that decrease in the rate constants is not strictly related to the increase in the ionic strength³ as is evident on comparing the rate constants and the ionic strengths contributed by 0.0625*M*- MgSO_4 and 0.25*M*- KNO_3 , where though the ionic strengths are equal, the rate constants differ widely. Evidently there is considerable specific effect of the ions; cation K^+ and anions SO_4^{2-} and NO_3^- have remarkable retarding influence.

Effect of Temperature.—The kinetics of this reaction was studied at different temperatures. The results are recorded in Table VII.

TABLE VII

Temp.	..	25°	30°	35°	40°	45°
$k \times 10^4$ (min ⁻¹)	..	26.49	34.68	46.42	68.64	97.92

From the above data the average values of the energy and entropy of activation were found to be 12303 cal. and -31.83 e.u. respectively.

DISCUSSION

Various mechanisms for the uncatalysed reaction involving peroxodisulphate have been suggested on the basis that anion ($\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$) yields the radical $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$, which initiates the oxidation reactions. If monovalent silver ion is present, the same is oxidised to higher valent state, bivalent or even trivalent, and this higher valent silver acts as an oxidising agent for a reducing substrate. Thus

An alternative initial step⁵ has been also suggested to explain the catalytic effect of silver ions.

followed by either

or

The formation of bivalent silver (Ag^{2+}) has also been suggested by the reaction:

The exact nature of the higher valent silver, thus formed as an intermediate for the oxidation of reducing substrate, is still obscure. The formation of Ag^{3+} has, however,

5. Bekier and Kijowski, *Chem. Abs.*, 1936, 30, 3306; Chaltykyan and Bellerian, *ibid.*, 1958, 52, 19054.

been proposed by Ghosh *et al.*⁵, Yost *et al.*⁶, and Malaguti⁷ support the view for the formation of higher valent silver (Ag^{II}) as an intermediate in these oxidations. The results obtained show that the velocities of oxidations are proportional to silver ion and peroxodisulphate concentrations (Table IV). Thus for the silver-catalysed reactions of peroxodisulphate, the loss of the oxidant may be expressed by the relation:

$$-\frac{d[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]}{dt} = K[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}][\text{Ag}^+]$$

and the reaction is of zero order with respect to the reducing substrate. Our investigations have, however, shown that increasing concentrations of lactic acid have depressing effect on the rate of the reaction. We are thus led to suggest the following mechanism of the catalysed oxidation of lactic acid by peroxodisulphate:

The above reaction for the formation of Ag^{3+} , the oxidation-reduction process, involves a two-electron transfer in one step, which has been said to be not feasible by Haber and Weiss⁸ and Evans⁹. It may, however, be easily shown that Ag^{3+} is formed from monovalent silver ion (Ag^{1+}) in two steps of oxidation. The equation (1) represents the reaction between the two oppositely charged ions and the coulombic forces will enhance the rate of the reaction. Any salt containing SO_4^{2-} ion will inhibit this process and our results on the salt effect are consistent with the above equation.

The Ag^{3+} formed, as shown above, reacts with lactic acid as:

The concentration or the amount of Ag^{3+} is small and that of lactic acid used in our experiments is large. It is well known that acetic acid forms a co-ordinate complex with trivalent manganese (Mn^{3+}) and this property is likely to be more evident with a monobasic organic acid with a hydroxyl group. It is possible that trivalent silver (Ag^{3+}) is partially removed as a stable complex and if equation (2) is a rate-determining one, the increasing concentrations of lactic acid will inhibit its own oxidation when the concentration of Ag^{3+} is lowered in the way described. Hence the order with respect to lactic acid may be fractional and negative (Table II). Levitt and Malinowski³ studied the oxidation of isopropyl alcohol by potassium peroxodisulphate at higher temperatures and the oxidation occurred at the carbon atom attached to the hydroxyl group. If it occurs so with lactic acid, we have

6. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1955, 51, 925.

7. *Anal. Chim. Rome*, 1955, 41, 241.

8. *Disc. Faraday Soc.*, 1947, 2, 168.

9. *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1946, 42, 101.

In other words, pyruvic acid will be the first oxidised product. We have, however, seen that pyruvic acid in presence of peroxodisulphate and silver ions of the concentration used at the temperatures of these experiments is oxidised very slowly and it does not yield aldehyde easily. It may therefore be concluded that oxidation of lactic acid occurs mainly, as shown by equation (2), *i.e.*, the COOH is detached as CO₂ and an OH group is substituted as shown in the equation.

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Kinetics of Oxidation of Glycerol by Potassium Peroxodisulphate in Presence of Silver Ions

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Oxidation of glycerol by peroxodisulphate by itself is slow even at 45°, but in presence of silver ions it proceeds with a measurable velocity. Kinetic study reveals that the rate is proportional to the concentration of the catalyst (silver ions) and that its order is unity with respect to the oxidant, but it is of zero order with respect to the reducing substrate. The products of oxidation of glycerol have been found to be formaldehyde, formic acid, acetaldehyde, and acetic acid, depending on the concentration of glycerol and temperature of the reaction. A mechanism for the catalytic action of silver ions has been suggested and the various oxidation compounds formed are ascribed to two side reactions. The energy and entropy of activation between 30° and 35° have also been determined.

Kinetics of the oxidation of organic compounds by peroxodisulphate has been little studied. According to King and Steinbach¹, the oxidation of oxalic acid by this oxidant is erratic and is susceptible to impurities. In the present investigation, by the use of redistilled water as the medium, fairly reproducible results have been obtained. Among several oxidising agents tried, the kinetics of the oxidation of glycerol by peroxodisulphate, catalysed by silver ions, has been reported in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental procedure adopted was the same as reported in an earlier paper^{1a}. Measured volumes of the reaction mixture were withdrawn at different intervals and un-

1. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **52**, 4779.
- 1a. This issue, p. 307.